

The creative response to Covid-19: R&D, internationalisation and the crisis.

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We examined R&D and internationalisation activities of Austrian companies during the Covid-19 crisis with firm-level data that cover the period 2019-21. The results show a wide variation in their reactions to the crisis, between high growth and considerable decreases of R&D expenditures, as well as differences in internationalisation. The most striking result of our analysis is that the behaviour of firms during Covid-19 does not fit with the predictions we found in the literature. In contrast to the literature which mostly assumes that firms reduce R&D activities during crisis, we find a lot of firms with growing R&D expenditures in the period. In Schumpeter's words, 'creative responses' were frequent, and even seemed to prevail over 'adaptive' response in some variables. Firms with an ex-ante low R&D intensity on average performed better than R&D intensive, high-technology firms. This may point to the importance of low opportunity costs for intensifying R&D activities during a crisis. Moreover, firms which received more public funding for R&D performed significantly better during the crisis than firms with lower or no public funding.

This research project was conducted with data from the Austrian Micro Data Center (AMDC). The AMDC is a research data infrastructure facility of Statistics Austria that enables research on micro data processed in compliance with data protection regulations

1. Introduction

How do innovation and research and development (R&D) activities in firms react to a crisis? Do enterprises reduce these activities to adjust their costs to decreasing market demand? Or do they increase innovative activities and R&D to be better prepared for the following economic upswing?

Joseph Schumpeter (1947) argued that firms react to changes in their environment by adaptive or creative responses. Adaptive response means that the firm reacts in a way “that traditional theory describes” (Schumpeter, 1947, p. 150). Creative response, in contrast, takes place “whenever the economy or an industry or some firms in an industry do something else, something that is outside of the range of existing practice” (ibid).

Schumpeter’s distinction between adaptive and creative response is readily applicable to the reactions of enterprises to Covid-19 pandemic. Most of the literature (the “traditional literature” in Schumpeter’s words) assumes a pro-cyclical response of enterprises to an economic crisis to that enterprises reduce R&D and innovation during a recession (Barlevy, 2007; Ouyang, 2011; Fabrizio and Tzolmon, 2014). Studies based of microdata from the Global Financial Crisis of 2008/09, however, point to a number of examples of counter-cyclical innovation response (Paunov, 2012; Rammer, 2012; Archibugi et al., 2013; Rammer and Schubert, 2018).

This paper wants to investigate the heterogeneity among firms in their reaction to the crisis regarding research and development and internationalisation. This will allow us to better understand how firms dealt with the Covid-19 crisis, and what types of firms were more or less resilient during the crisis, and how the crisis spurred or blocked innovation in firms. The paper is organized as follows; in the next chapter we present the literature background and our hypotheses, while chapter 3 and 4 introduce the data and our empirical approach. Results are found in chapter 5, while chapter 6 discusses some conclusions.

2. Background and hypotheses

Fluctuations of innovation activities in different stages of the business cycle have been the topic of a number of papers since the Global Financial Crisis of 2008/09 (Ouyang, 2011; Paunov, 2012; Archibugi et al., 2013; Berchicci et al., 2014; Fabrizio and Tzolmon, 2014; Dachs et al., 2017; Peters et al., 2022). The majority of this research indicates that enterprises react to an economic crisis by reducing R&D and innovation. This pattern is explained by two main factors:

First, liquidity constraints that force enterprises to use their financial means to activities that are essential for short-term survival. Innovation may be as less relevant than other business activities, at least in the short term. As a consequence, firms reduce their innovation activities during recessions (Himmelberg and Petersen, 1994; Aghion et al., 2010; Aghion et al., 2012).

Second, enterprises face worsening expectations of future demand during recessions which makes them cautious about the introduction of new products and higher R&D expenditures (Bloom, 2007). A similar effect arises when firms postpone the market introduction of innovations to periods of fast demand growth to maximize the expected profits of innovation (Barlevy, 2007; Fabrizio and Tsoimon, 2014).

There are, however, also arguments that speak in favor of more – not less – innovation during a crisis. During recessions, decreases in turnover may lead to unemployed resources which can be used for innovation, training, or other productivity-enhancing activities. Moreover the opportunity costs of innovation – in terms of forgone profits – may be much lower during a recession (Aghion and Saint-Paul, 1998). Recessions also lead to a re-allocation of resources from low-productivity to higher-productivity firms by forcing low-productivity firms out of the market, which Schumpeter has labelled the ‘cleansing effect’ by (Legrand and Hagemann, 2017). The cleansing effect may lead to counter-cyclical innovation behavior when firms can use these freed resources for their innovation activities. In the medium-term innovativeness may improve due to increasing knowledge spillovers from other innovative firms.

The majority of studies reveal a pro-cyclical reaction by enterprises, but this pattern far from being unambiguous, as Rammer (2012), Archibugi et al. (2013), or Berchicci et al. (2014) report. According to Rammer (2012), 34% of all German enterprises increased their innovation activities during the 2008/09 crisis, while 33% reduced innovation, while the remaining companies reported no changes in their innovation activities. Rammer also shows considerable differences in innovation behavior during the crisis between enterprises of different sectors. This heterogeneity may also explain the lack of clear aggregate results.

The crisis which followed the outbreak of Covid-19 differed from previous crises in some important factors which may have also influenced innovation (Trunschke et al., 2023). A first unique factor were lockdowns and social distancing to contain the spread of the SARS-CoV-2 virus which causes Covid-19. Moreover, Covid-19 was also accompanied by severe supply chain disruptions. Both factors have led to a reduced production and consumption of goods and services, and decreasing revenues of companies (Bloom et al., 2021; Brodeur et al., 2021). These effects were uneven across sectors and companies; sectors where face-to-face interaction is important suffered most, while information services or the suppliers of medical equipment even faced a surge in demand during the crisis. Moreover, a ‘sense of crisis’ and the immediate need to replace face-to-face communication and introduce work-from-home to continue operations may have spurred

innovation related to digital technologies in companies (Kraus et al., 2020; Clauss et al., 2022). This fits with Taalbi (2017) who describes innovations as reactions to discrete events.

These differences may have transferred into differences in the innovation responses of companies to the crisis of 2020/21. Empirical evidence by the OECD (2023, p. 20) confirms large variations in the changes of R&D expenditures at sectoral level.

This leads to the first hypothesis:

H1: There are significant differences in the response of companies to the crisis in terms of R&D, digitalization, and internationalization.

The innovation literature assumes that the size of a company, the sector it operates and its technology intensity, or the ownership status determines to a considerable degree innovation activity of the firm (Brouwer and Kleinknecht, 1996; Marsili, 2001; Dachs et al., 2008; Cohen, 2010; Peneder, 2010; Coad et al., 2018). We assume that these factors also help to explain the differences in the responses to the crisis we expected in H1:

H2: The differences in the response of companies to the crisis are related to size, sector, ownership, or technology intensity.

Lockdowns and social distancing caused considerable economic losses for enterprises. According to Eurostat's Structural Business Statistics (European Commission, 2023), the EU's industrial production decreased by 7.3 % from 2019 to 2020, with the largest slump in the production of capital goods (-11.1 %). A 12% decrease was reported for non-financial services (excluding trade). Some of these costs were compensated by governments via rescue packages. In Austria, the government provided 49.6 bn EUR or 12.6 percent of the 2019 GDP to ease the economic effects of Covid-19 (Loretz et al., 2021). However, as generous they may have been, these funds may have arrived too late for some firms to continue R&D activities. Liquidity have certainly been an advantage during the Covid-19 crisis. We assume that large firms with internal financial resources and easy access to credit markets (Archibugi et al., 2013) or foreign-owned firms which can rely on the resources of their enterprise group (Kolasa et al., 2010) are better prepared to continue R&D during a crisis than small or medium-sized firms which cannot rely on these assets. Financial strength to some degree also determined likelihood of continuing R&D during the last crisis (Rammer and Schubert, 2018).

H3: R&D activities in large firms and foreign subsidiaries with easier access to funding were more resilient during the crisis.

Labs and other technical facilities at universities, public research organizations, but also in companies have been closed for longer periods of time during 2020 and 2021 (Paunov and Planes-Satorra, 2021). As a result,

projects were delayed due to limited access to these facilities. Social distancing and travel restrictions may have also hampered the exchange of ideas and knowledge, which often takes place face-to-face (Foray, 2004). This has been an obstacle for science-based sectors in particular which depend much more on cooperation with universities than low-technology sectors:

H4: R&D activities have decreased stronger in science-based industries than in other sectors.

Another feature of the Covid-19 crisis which distinguished it from previous crises were severe supply chain disruptions (WTO, 2021). COVID-19 stopped or delayed supplies across the world and affected virtually every industry, from manufacturing and retail to healthcare and information technology. However, not every industry or firm was affected equally, and the degree of backward integration into GVCs – which can be measured by the dependency of a firm on imports – played a large role in mitigating or augmenting the effects of these disruptions (Espitia et al., 2022).

H5: Strong backwards GVC integration was a disadvantage during the crisis, so its negative effect was larger for highly internationalized firms due to GVC disruptions.

3. Data

We employ firm-level data from Statistics Austria for the period 2019-21. The database is compiled from the results of three different surveys: Austrian structural business statistics (Leistungs- und Strukturerhebung), R&D survey, and data on imports and exports at firm level. These data sets have been matched at the firm level.

And finally include 2,859 firms which reported R&D activities for 2019 and 2021. Another 1,100 firms provided data for 2019, but not for 2021. We do not know why these are missing. It may be that these firms have stopped their R&D activities; however, it may also be that they simply did not answer the 2021 survey, so the conclusion that these firms exited R&D activities seems too far-reaching.

4. Approach

The analysis proceeds in two steps: first, we divide the sample into different sub-groups that help us to grasp the heterogeneity in the data and understand what has changed between 2019 and 2021. Second, we employ descriptive statistics and regressions to link these changes to external factors.

Firms are categorized in two ways: first, we divided the whole sample into five quantiles according to the percentage change of R&D expenditures between 2019 and 2021 to identify those firms with high growth, medium growth, no growth, medium losses, or huge losses in R&D expenditures.

As a second approach, we categorized the firms of the sample according to absolute R&D expenditures and R&D intensity (R&D expenditures divided by turnover) into four groups (Dachs and Drach, 2019):

- *Moderate R&D performers* with a R&D intensity of less than 7% (the mean intensity across all firms).
- *R&D professionals* with an R&D intensity of more than 7% and less than 2.5 Mio EUR R&D expenditures which is the mean of R&D expenditures.
- *R&D Leaders* with R&D intensities of 7% and more but less than 50%, and R&D expenditures of more than 2.5 EUR.
- *R&D Centers* with R&D intensities of 50% or more and R&D expenditures of more than 2.5 EUR.

These four classes account for the heterogeneity among R&D active firms in Austria. Besides manufacturing and services firms where investing in R&D is a strategy to increase competitiveness, the Austrian business sector also includes a number of firms that provide R&D as their main product. Examples are found among technology-intensive start-ups or specialized suppliers of knowledge. Moreover, some research and technology organizations including AIT, but also corporate R&D centers affiliated to foreign multinationals are incorporated as enterprises.

5. Results

Austria's gross domestic product dropped by 6.6% from 2019 to 2020 according to Statistics Austria but could rebound in 2021 so that Austria's GDP in 2021 was two percent higher in 2021 compared to 2019. The enterprises in the sample performed better than the GDP, with turnover growth of 4.7% between 2019 and 2021. Aggregate R&D expenditures increased by 7%, while the share of imports and exports on turnover increased by 18.4% and 11.1%. These results indicate that the sample is certainly a positive selection of the Austrian firm population.

At the firm level, the data show a huge variation in the growth of R&D expenditures and intensities between 2019 and 2021. We further divided the sample according to the change of R&D expenditures into five quantiles with 572 firms each (see Table 1). R&D expenditures in the lowest quantile dropped by a median value of -60%, while it was -20% in the second lowest quantile. On the other end of the distribution, the growth rate was 166% in the highest quantile and 30% in the second highest quantile. This leaves on fifth of the sample which stagnated at a median growth rate of 2.3%. So, extremes were the norm, not the exception during 2019-21. There is a clear association between R&D expenditures growth and turnover growth which increases when moving to higher quantiles. The combination of falling turnover and decreasing R&D expenditures results that the lowest R&D intensity is found in the first quartile. A high volatility in R&D expenditures is related to small firm sizes. The firms in the highest and in the lowest quantiles show the

smallest average firm size. Quite surprisingly, these two quantiles also reveal the highest shares of public funding on R&D expenditures.

The picture with respect to internationalization is less heterogenous. The changes in exports are highest in the middle and in the highest quantile, and lowest in the first quantile. This indicates a positive relationship between the change in R&D expenditures and export performance. Imports as a share of turnover – which we use as an indicator of backward GVC integration – increased in all quantiles, but most strongly in the in the highest quantile. Imports as a share of turnover in 2019 quite even across the quantiles which indicates that ex-ante GVC integration was not an important influence for the crisis reaction.

We also constructed an experimental indicator for backshoring; backshoring firms are defined as those enterprises that have reduced imports by at least 20% while expanding their turnover by at least five percent. Results indicate that 12% of all firms fell under this backshoring definition. If we exclude firms with less than 20% to match the sample definition of the European Manufacturing Survey which also includes backshoring, the data reveal a share of nine percent backshoring firms, which is slightly above the share of seven percent reported by the EMS for Austria in 2021 (Orsulic et al., 2023). However, the results contradict the results of the EMS because the report a higher backshoring share for smaller firms. Backshoring is more frequent in the lower and higher quantiles, and lowest in the middle quantile.

One answer why we see so much heterogeneity in the responses to the crisis lies in the structural and strategic differences between the actors. For some of them, such as manufacturing firms in low-tech sectors, R&D is only a minor activity, while it is the main activity of other firms such as technology-based start-ups. We conceptualized these structural differences in a typology of R&D-active firms that differentiates between four types of firms depending on their R&D intensity and total R&D expenditures (see also Dachs and Drach, 2019): moderate R&D performers with a lower-than-average R&D intensity; R&D professionals – firms with low absolute R&D expenditures, but very high R&D intensities; R&D leaders with above-average R&D intensities and high absolute R&D expenditures; and R&D centers with very high R&D intensities as well as high R&D expenditures. R&D professionals and R&D centers thus are firms where R&D is their main activity, and R&D expenditures account for the majority of their turnover. Accordingly, these two groups also devote considerably more of their R&D efforts on basic research.

Table 2 presents various indicators for these four groups and for the total sample. Moderate R&D performers and R&D professionals are the large majority of the sample, including 2,579 firms. However, they only account for less than 40% of total R&D expenditures. The group of R&D Leaders, in contrast, only includes 190 firms, but accounts for half of the R&D expenditures. There are also huge differences in median R&D intensities, ranging from 2% for moderate R&D performers to 99% in R&D Centers.

All four groups performed differently during the crisis. While R&D professionals, R&D centers, and moderate R&D performers were able to increase their median R&D expenditures, while R&D leaders suffered losses of around three percent. Moderate R&D performers but also R&D centers in particular were able to significantly increase R&D expenditures which is surprising since these two groups lie at the opposite ends of the spectrum. Median R&D intensities decreased in all four groups, while mean intensities increased in two of the four groups with adds to the picture of heterogeneity. Starting from a lower level in 2019, R&D centers saw the highest change in exports and the second highest change in imports, with changes in imports more evenly distributed than the changes in exports.

Quite surprisingly, the data indicates that moderate R&D performers – firms with below-average R&D intensity – were one of the winners of the crisis, while R&D Leaders were on the losing side. Moderate R&D performers reveal the highest mean and the second highest median growth rate of R&D expenditures. As a consequence, the concentration of R&D expenditures in the top 10th quantile decreased in Austria from 2019 to 2021.

Hypothesis H3 assumes that large firms and foreign subsidiaries with access to funding from foreign company headquarters were more resilient during the crisis. Moreover, in H4 we assume that science-based sectors suffered more than other sectors due to limited opportunities to co-operate with universities during the lock-downs, and H5 stated that firms with a strong backward links in GVC suffered more than other enterprises.

The growth quantiles provide some empirical evidence to test these claims. Average firm size as well as the share of foreign-owned firms are lowest in the first and the fifth quantile, which does not support H3. Moreover, the share of funding from enterprises including headquarters from abroad is highest in the middle quantile, and the differences are too small to assume an effect on the change of R&D expenditures. Based on these results, we refute H3.

The share of basic and applied research on R&D activities is quite the same in all quantiles, so there is no support H4. However, if we look at the four groups discussed above, it becomes clear that moderate R&D performers with a below-average research share performed best during the crisis, while the research-intensive R&D Professionals suffered losses. R&D Centers which reveal the highest research intensity also reveal a below-average growth of R&D expenditures. So there is some evidence that research intensive activities suffered more during the crisis than activities which focus on experimental development.

Finally, we investigate the relationship between R&D performance during the crisis and internationalisation. The share of imports on turnover is highest in the lowest and the highest quantile, and lowest in the middle quantile. We can regard this as an indication that firms with a higher exposure to global value chains revealed more extreme reactions to the crisis. However, if we look at the changes in imports, we see only

little variation with the exception of the highest quantile which imported 42% more in 2021 than in 2019. We do not see that the descriptive statistics support H5.

We further test these hypotheses with regression analysis where the percentage change of R&D expenditures between 2019 and 2021 is the dependent variable (Table 3). Firm size, the share of public funding and foreign ownership, the change in turnover between 2019 and 2021, R&D intensity in 2019, the share of imports on turnover, and the four groups of firms described above are independent variables.

A negative and highly significant coefficient for firm size rejects the hypothesis that large firms were more resilient during the crisis. Not large, but smaller firms did better during the crisis. We could also not find significant differences with respect to foreign ownership which would support H3. However, a higher share of public funding for R&D is positively related to the change in R&D expenditures. Obviously, public funding has taken over the role of internal funds in softening the effects of the crisis on R&D. The two main funding instruments for business R&D in Austria, tax credits for R&D and R&D grants have considerably increased from 2019 to 2021.

Exposure to GVCs and GVC disruptions did not seem to have an impact on R&D; the share of imports on turnover in 2019 is not significantly related to changes in R&D expenditures. Results on H4 are not conclusive: on the one hand, we find that the sectors with the highest share of research reveal a significantly negative coefficient in the regression. On the other hand, a significant relationship between the share of research on turnover and the change in R&D expenditures cannot be established.

There are also significant differences in the regression between the four groups discussed above; all three groups reveal a negative coefficient when tested against moderate R&D performers, which indicates that these firms were more resilient during the crisis than the other three. In particular, R&D centers and R&D professionals show high negative coefficients, pointing out that these types of firms were more severely affected by the crisis than the other two, all other factors held constant.

6. Conclusions

We examined R&D and internationalisation activities of Austrian companies during the Covid-19 crisis with firm-level data that cover the period 2019-21. The results show a wide variation in their reactions to the crisis, between high growth and considerable decreases of R&D expenditures, as well as differences in internationalisation. In Schumpeter's words, 'creative responses' were frequent, and even seemed to prevail over 'adaptive' response in some variables.

Firms with an ex-ante low R&D intensity on average performed better than R&D intensive, high-technology firms. This may point to the importance of low opportunity costs for intensifying R&D activities during a

crisis. Moreover, firms which received more public funding for R&D performed significantly better during the crisis than firms with lower or no public funding.

The most striking result of our analysis is that the behaviour of firms during Covid-19 does not fit with the predictions we found in the literature. In contrast to the literature which mostly assumes that firms reduce R&D activities during crisis, we find a lot of firms with growing R&D expenditures in the period. There are roughly the same number of firms with growing and decreasing R&D expenditures in the period 2019-21.

This observation allows different conclusions. A first reason for the misfit may be the specific character of the Covid-19 crisis which was mainly a health crisis which later emerged into an economic crisis. At no time, it was a crisis of the market economy or of the financial system, like the crisis of 2008/09. The drop in economic sentiment as measured by the Economic Sentiment Indicator of the European Commission (DG ECFIN, 2023) was deeper but lasted shorter than in 2008/09. The crisis was over after one year in mid-2021 with a sharp rebound of economic activity. This may have avoided negative expectations of the future economic development that have been identified as a reason for decreasing R&D activity by prior research (Bloom, 2007).

Another factor which contributed to a short recession with less severe effects on R&D activities were the relief packages by national governments. The Austrian government provided 49.6 billion EUR or 12.6 percent of 2019 GDP to shield enterprises from the negative consequences of the crisis. Support included compensations for short-term work arrangements, liquidity support for firms, and public loan guarantees (IMF, 2021). A main argument in the literature is that R&D activities in firms suffer during the crisis due to liquidity constraints; liquidity, however, was provided by the government so we may assume that the relief packages also had a positive effect on R&D, even if they did not directly target R&D. Moreover, there was a massive increase in public funding for R&D between 2019 and 2021. The regression results suggest that this increase contributed to a stabilization of the R&D activities in Austrian firms during this period.

7. Literature

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Table 1: Quantiles of firms according to their change in R&D expenditures between 2019 and 2021.

Quantiles	Firm size	R&D intensity			R&D expenditures	Turnover	Public funding	Funding from abroad	Basic and applied research	Exports	Imports	Imports
	Avr no of employees	2019	2021	Change, %points	Change in, %	Change, %	Share on total R&D	Share on total R&D	Share on total R&D	Change, %	Share of turnover	Change, %
1	116	9.9%	3.8%	-6.2%	-6.3%	1.6%	18%	2.6%	42.6%	0.9%	42%	4.1%
2	230	12.2%	8.2%	-4.0%	-2.1%	1.5%	16%	3.0%	42.9%	5.6%	38%	5.6%
3	193	1.4%	0.8%	-0.6%	0.3%	0.4%	15%	3.8%	42.7%	42.3%	35%	4.5%
4	194	2.4%	3.6%	1.2%	3.3%	6.1%	16%	2.3%	42.4%	8.48%	36%	4.3%
5	149	11.0%	14.9%	3.9%	39.9%	13.9%	17%	2.4%	42.9%	34.1%	43%	42.1%
Total	176	7.4%	6.3%	-1.1%	7.0%	4.7%	16%	2.8%	42.7%	18.4%	39%	11.1%

Source: R&D survey by Statistics Austria, own calculations

Table 2: Groups of firms according to R&D intensity and absolute R&D expenditures between 2019 and 2021.

Group	No of firms	R&D intensity			R&D expenditures	Turnover	Public funding	Funding from abroad	Basic and applied research	Exports	Imports	Imports
		2019	2021	Change, %points	Change, %	Change, %	Share on total R&D	Share on total R&D	Share on total R&D	Change, %	Share of turnover	Change, %
Moderate R&D	1,232	0.02%	0.04%	0.02%	10.7%	0.1%	11.3%	1.1%	39.7%	17.0%	32%	11.7%
R&D Professionals	1,347	12.22%	9.67%	-2.56%	5.0%	9.7%	20.8%	3.4%	46.0%	18.3%	49%	13.2%
R&D Leaders	190	0.18%	0.16%	-0.02%	-0.3%	0.1%	10.5%	5.9%	34.0%	21.9%	24%	0.6%
R&D Centers	90	52.91%	54.23%	1.32%	1.2%	3.2%	25.1%	11.2%	52.0%	34.3%	17%	12.1%
Total	2,859	7.36%	6.26%	-1.10%	7.0%	4.7%	16.1%	2.8%	42.7%	18.4%	39%	11.1%

Source: R&D survey by Statistics Austria, own calculations

Table 3: Regression results

Independent variable	Coefficient	Std. err.	t	P> t	[95% conf interval]	
Log of employees	-36.8132	5.7467	-6.410	0.000	-48.083	-25.543
Share of public funding	0.9053	0.4453	2.030	0.042	0.032	1.779
Sh. of funding from abroad	7.6866	18.1157	0.420	0.671	-27.840	43.213
Share of research	0.5008	0.2066	2.420	0.015	0.096	0.906
Change in turnover	0.0002	0.0009	0.250	0.806	-0.001	0.002
Share of imports	0.0007	0.0040	0.160	0.871	-0.007	0.009
Group: R&D Professionals	-135.7158	21.3962	-6.340	0.000	-177.676	-93.756
Group: R&D Leaders	-57.2953	27.3924	-2.090	0.037	-111.015	-3.576
Group: R&D Centers	-119.4516	40.1573	-2.970	0.003	-198.204	-40.699
_cons	226.5903	30.8492	7.350	0.000	166.092	287.089

Source: R&D survey by Statistics Austria, own calculations

Base case: Moderate R&D performers